

Enhancing Robust Autonomy of ROS 2 Systems: Usable Formal Verification and Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Reliable autonomy in robotic systems requires deliberation mechanisms capable of handling dynamic environments robustly. However, despite their potential for improving system robustness, formal verification techniques like model checking remain uncommon in the robotics domain due to usability and accessibility challenges. This work synthesizes insights from two studies on robotic deliberation system development, identifying key challenges in designing and debugging deliberation mechanisms. Based on these insights, solutions to improve development workflows and ensure system robustness are discussed. One proposal is the introduction of High-Level SCXML (HL-SCXML) to model system components including both Robot Operating System 2 (ROS 2) and Behavior Tree (BT) features. AS2FM (Autonomous Systems to Formal Models) is a tool that allows statistical model checking for ROS 2-based systems by translating a system model given in HL-SCXML format into JANI, enabling the verification of system properties at design-time. To enhance usability, we propose integrating AS2FM with model-driven engineering (MDE) tools such as Papyrus for Robotics, automating the generation of HL-SCXML models, reducing manual effort. Additionally, we present an approach leveraging reinforcement learning using scene graphs, enabling autonomous robots to navigate in unknown environments more robustly. Combining the formal verification and learning approaches aims to practically ensure reliable and adaptable autonomy of robotic systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous robotic systems must operate reliably in unpredictable environments, making robust deliberation a critical requirement. Despite advances in deliberation techniques such as Behavior Trees (BTs) [1] and Finite State Machines (FSMs) [2], ensuring system-wide robustness remains a challenge [3].

Formal verification methods, such as statistical model checking (SMC) [4], [5], provide rigorous guarantees but are often difficult to integrate into the development processes in the robotics domain due to their complexity, scalability, and accessibility in terms of input formats. In this work, we explore usability challenges of formal verification in robotics based on two surveys among robotic software developers and propose concrete solutions in form of modeling formats and tools to increase accessibility and effectiveness.

One solution is AS2FM (Autonomous Systems to Formal Models) [6], a tool that translates ROS 2 system models into JANI [7], a standard format for quantitative model checking.

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ROS 2 system models, the BT functionalities, and communication features are expressed in an High-Level State Chart XML format explicitly designed for this purpose. AS2FM and its input format HL-SCXML have been validated through user feedback in a survey and benchmarking studies on robotics use cases have been performed, demonstrating its ability to identify system flaws at design-time [6], [8]. However, its current reliance on manually written HL-SCXML models presents a usability barrier. To address this, we propose an integration with Papyrus for Robotics (P4R) [9], allowing for automatic generation of HL-SCXML models.

In addition to the focus on formal verification, we present a second approach for making robot deliberation more robust. We increase the robot’s situation awareness in unknown environments through reinforcement learning (RL) by providing scene graphs as input. Scene graphs are built from the robot’s sensor data, capturing structural and geometric relationships between detected objects and their effect on robot navigation [10]. Our aim is to autonomously learn these relationships during robot operation, such that the robot can decide whether to circumvent or interact with known and new objects in the environment.

Finally, the two lines of work on model checking autonomous ROS 2 systems including the BT, and reinforcement learning on the scene graph for more robust navigation in unknown environments can be combined by using verification techniques for neural networks (NNs), like in [11], which ensure the quality of the learned models, leading to even more adaptable robotic autonomy.

II. IMPROVING USABILITY OF FORMAL VERIFICATION FOR ROS 2 SYSTEMS

Two surveys [12], [13], [8] were conducted among developers of autonomous robots to investigate challenges and methodological needs in building robust robotic deliberation systems. The findings of the first one, available online ¹ [13], highlighted that developers have a high preference for expressing deliberation logics in terms of Behavior Trees (BTs) (77.97%) and Finite State Machines (FSMs) (64.41%). Developers value BTs for their modularity and clarity but report difficulties in debugging and formally verifying them. Most developers use simulation (88.14%) or manual testing (77.97%) but lack systematic verification methods. Only 15.25% of the respondents currently use model checking but 77.58% of the participants expressed a need for more systematic verification approaches, suggesting a lack of accessible

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tooling. 81.03% of developers do not use formal models (e.g., Markovian Processes) due to complexity and high effort. However, 43.86% indicated they would adopt formal methods if they were more accessible and provided tangible benefits. To improve the situation, developers emphasized the need for user-friendly interfaces, clear documentation, and integration with existing tools.

Taking those findings into account, we developed AS2FM (Autonomous Systems to Formal Models) [6], and provided it as an open-source tool.² AS2FM uses HL-SCXML as a modeling language to describe robotic systems, including their communication, behavior, and decision-making processes. HL-SCXML extends standard SCXML by incorporating ROS 2 interfaces, Behavior Tree elements, and non-deterministic transitions. This allows developers to model entire autonomous systems in a structured, hierarchical, and modular manner. To model ROS 2 communication interfaces, topics, services, and actions are represented as event-based interactions between state machines. Behavior Trees can be loaded using the same format as provided by BehaviorTree.CPP, to allow for smooth interoperability with existing BT-based control structures. BT plugins are developed using HL-SCXML. In addition, timers and non-deterministic transitions can be expressed in this format, which is essential for modeling real-world robotic systems often operating under uncertainty.

AS2FM then translates HL-SCXML models into JANI [7], a standard format used as input for statistical model checkers. By leveraging JANI-compatible state-of-the-art tools, such as SMC Storm [14], AS2FM enables offline verification of temporal properties, providing robustness guarantees. The translation process from the real system into an HL-SCXML model ensures that system properties can be formally verified before system deployment, reducing costly field tests and the likelihood of failures in real-world operations.

After AS2FM has been released, a second survey at ROSCon 2024 [8] compared different tools for robotic deliberation and confirmed that AS2FM provides valuable insights for developers but better onboarding to use the tool and especially write the input models is required. The results of the entire survey are available online.³ Participants recommended to automate the extraction of the formal model from the real system code to reduce the modeling gap between the real system and the model, as well as the time to construct such a model. This reveals that the major obstacle in the adoption of formal verification techniques, not only in robotics, is the need for hand-written models of the system under investigation, like HL-SCXML representations.

To enhance usability, we propose to link AS2FM with model-driven engineering (MDE) tools like Papyrus for Robotics⁴ (P4R) [9], making formal verification a seamless part of the development workflow. P4R provides graphical modeling capabilities, which would allow roboticists to de-

fine the deliberation logic at a higher abstraction level. These models can then be automatically translated into the HL-SCXML format accepted as input by AS2FM, eliminating the need for error-prone and time-consuming manual encoding, thereby reducing the gap between the real system and the model. This integration with MDE tools makes formal verification more accessible by leveraging visual design paradigms familiar to robotic software engineers. It also improves consistency and reduces errors, as models are systematically generated rather than manually crafted. By streamlining the pipeline from high-level design to formal verification, we lower the entry barrier for developers who, according to the surveys, often lack expertise in formal methods.

III. SITUATION LEARNING FOR ROBUST DELIBERATION

While formal verification ensures correctness under modeled conditions, real robotic systems also require robust adaptability to unforeseen scenarios. To complement formal methods, we propose leveraging reinforcement learning [15] giving scene graphs derived from perception as input. Scene graphs [10] provide a structured representation of the robot's environment, capturing relationships between detected objects and their effect on robot navigation. By training RL agents using these scene graphs, autonomous robots can learn navigation strategies for unknown environments, e.g., by avoiding to get stuck on certain obstacles, or by interacting with obstacles in terms of pushing them away in case they are classified as movable.

In a second step, the RL approach described above can be combined with formal verification to prove robustness of the learned behavior of the robotic system. There are verification techniques available ensuring the quality of the NN trained by the reinforcement learning algorithms [11]. This enables the design of systems with robust deliberation capabilities, leveraging the predictive power of formal verification in combination with the adaptive capabilities of machine learning. This combination of methods ensures continuous operation of the robotic system without failure even when encountering unexpected obstacles.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This work presents AS2FM as a tool for model checking robot deliberation, addresses key usability challenges in formal verification for ROS 2-based robotic systems, and proposes two main improvements: (1) an MDE-based approach for automatically generating HL-SCXML models to be used in AS2FM, and (2) an RL-based strategy for learning robust navigation policies in unknown environments. These enhancements aim to foster robust robot behavior by bridging the gap between formal verification and practical usability in robotics system engineering, making robust autonomy more achievable. Future work includes implementing the proposed P4R-AS2FM integration and further exploring the combination of formal methods with machine learning-driven methods for autonomous robots.

²<https://convince-project.github.io/AS2FM/>

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14051492>

⁴<https://eclipse.dev/papyrus/components/robotics/>

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